

I BIG DATA FOR BUSINESS IN EUROPE

The use of Big Data for business purposes grew by 66% between 2016 and 2021 in DESI countries

The DESI database parses the Big Data variable. This variable considers at country level the percentage of companies that analyze Big Data regardless of the data sources they use. The data refer to the period 2016-2021. The United Kingdom is excluded from the list of DESI countries.

Ranking of DESI countries for use of Big Data in 2021. Malta is in first place for the percentage of companies that use Big Data for business purposes with a value of 8.18%, followed by the Netherlands with a value of 7.28% and from Denmark with an amount of 7.209%. In the middle of the table there is Portugal with an amount of 2.82%, followed by Lithuania with a value of 2.81% and Estonia with an amount equal to 2.63%. Cyprus closed the ranking with an amount of 1.64%, Slovakia with a value of 1.49% and Romania with 1.35%.

Ranking of DESI countries by percentage change in the use of big data for business purposes between 2016 and 2021. Germany ranks first in terms of the percentage change in the use of Big Data for business purposes with a value of 283.62% equal to an amount of 3.52 units, followed by Cyprus with an amount of 189.24% equal to an amount of 1.08 units, and by Denmark with an amount of 183.82% equal to an amount of 4.67 units. In the middle of the table there is Ireland with an amount of 69.23% equal to an amount of 2.47 units, followed by Latvia with a variation of 67.46% equal to an amount of 0.92 units, and Belgium. with a value of 65.43% equal to an amount of 2.41 units. Slovenia closes the ranking with an amount equal to -26.62% equal to an amount of -0.63 units, followed by Cyprus with a value equal to -36.15% equal to an amount of -0.84 units, and from Romania with an amount of -43.94% equal to an amount of 1,065 units. Overall, between 2016 and 2021 in DESI countries, the value of the use of Big Data for business purposes increased by 66.07% on average.

Clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. The data show the presence of the following clusters:

- Cluster 1: Austria, Luxembourg, Lithuania, Greece, Slovenia, Romania, Bulgaria, Germany, Poland, Italy, Hungary, Croatia, Portugal, France, Czech Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Slovakia;
- Cluster 2: Cyprus, Ireland, Finland, Malta, the Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden, Spain, Belgium.

Considering the cluster analysis, it appears that the median value of cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 6.07% while the median value of cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 2.39%. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives: $C1 = 6.07 > C2 = 2.39$. The data show that apart from some countries that have largely evolved from the point of view of the use of Big Data, there are others - and they are the vast majority - that do not have the ability to use Big Data for commercial enterprise purposes.

Network Analysis using the Manhattan distance. A network analysis is carried out below using the Manhattan distance. Two complex network structures and three simplified network structures are

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detected. There is a complex network structure between Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland and Latvia. Particularly:

- Hungary has a connection with Bulgaria for an amount of 0.12 units, a connection with Latvia for a value of 0.36;
- Bulgaria has a connection with Hungary for a value of 0.12, and with Latvia for an amount of 0.35 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Hungary for an amount of 0.36, and with Bulgaria for a value of 0.35, and with Poland for a value of 0.11.

There is a complex network structure between Slovenia, Sweden, Slovakia, Croatia and Spain. Particularly:

- Sweden has a connection with Slovenia for an amount equal to 0.34, with Slovakia for an amount equal to 0.25 and with Croatia for an amount equal to 0.24;
- Slovenia has a connection with Sweden for an amount equal to 0.34 units and with Slovakia for an amount equal to 0.18 units;
- Slovakia has a connection with Sweden for an amount equal to 0.25 and with Slovenia for an amount equal to 0.18;
- Croatia has a connection with Sweden for an amount equal to 0.24 and with Spain for an amount equal to 0.31.

Furthermore, there are some simplified and one-to-one network structures as indicated below, namely:

- There is a connection between Denmark and Lithuania for an amount equal to 0.095 units;
- There is a connection between Belgium and Ireland for an amount equal to 0.16;
- There is a connection between the Czech Republic and Italy for an amount equal to 0.25 units.

Conclusions. Although the use of Big Data for business purposes in Europe has significantly increased, marking a + 66%, it is still scarcely widespread in European countries. Companies do not know how to take advantage of the abundant supply of data on the web and therefore can lose significant profit and business opportunities. Furthermore, the job market has developed professional figures who have the skills to manage Big Data, or Data Scientists, who generally have conducted a PhD and can put together statistical and mathematical knowledge with tools. complex analytics to transform data into useful information for business decisions. Through these analyzes, companies can discover new markets and business opportunities, get to know their customers better, make price offers that are more sustainable, anticipate the competition and maximize market positioning. The use of Big Data is necessary for companies that want to grow in the phygital dimension, that is both physical and digital, maximizing the value of their products and services in the relationship with customers.

Declarations

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